

MENINGITIS IN NEONATES PRESENTING WITH NEONATAL SEPSIS AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Objective: The purpose of the research is to find out the meningitis in neonates presenting with neonatal sepsis

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study

Study Duration: 06 months from January 2024 to July 2024

Study Place: Department of Paediatrics, CMH Rawalpindi

Methods: 200 participants were enrolled using a WHO online calculator. Non-probability convenient sampling technique was applied to select neonates showing meningitis symptoms. Sepsis was confirmed through elevated CRP and abnormal hematological parameters. Variables like gestational age, birth weight, FOC, hemoglobin, and CRP were presented as mean \pm SD, while gender and delivery mode were shown as frequencies. SPSS 26 was used for data analysis and p -value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results: Among 200 neonates, 134 (67%) were males and 66 (33%) females. The mean gestational age, birth weight, and fronto-occipital circumference (FOC) were 34.4 weeks, 2872 g and 33.5 cm respectively. The mean CSF cell count was 383.03, while proteins and glucose averaged at 922 and 2.3, respectively. Mean CRP was 32.06. 24 patients (12%) were culture-positive. *E. coli* was found in 7 cases, *Acinetobacter baumannii* in 6, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 4. *E. coli* was resistant to ampicillin but sensitive to amikacin, ceftriaxone, gentamicin and meropenem.

Conclusion: Neonatal meningitis is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality, particularly in preterm and low-birth-weight neonates. Early diagnosis using cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis and effective targeted antimicrobial therapy are the most important rescue measures in managing this condition.

Introduction

Neonatal meningitis is a critical infectious disease characterized by inflammation of the meninges. It is often considered a severe manifestation of neonatal sepsis. It typically occurs within the first 28 days of life and substantially contributes to neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations with limited healthcare access and (Shane et al., 2017; Cortese et al., 2016). In China, recent

data reports a mortality rate of 9.1% and neurological complications in 5.9% of affected neonates (Collaborative Study Group for Neonatal Bacterial Meningitis, 2018). Neonatal meningitis can be of both an early or late onset.

Early onset neonatal sepsis is more dangerous with poor patient outcomes (Liu et al., 2020). Early-onset neonatal sepsis occurs within the first three days of life. It often results from vertical transmission of infection during

childbirth. Group B *Streptococcus* is the most predominant pathogen for early onset neonatal sepsis (Puopolo et al., 2019). Patients with conditions of amniotic fluid contamination, chorioamnionitis, short for gestation age and preterm early rupture of membranes develop early-onset neonatal sepsis.

Late-onset sepsis, occurring three days after birth of neonate, is caused by horizontal transmission from the hospital environment or invasive procedures such as total parenteral nutrition, vascular lines and airway support etc. Most common bacterial causes include GBS and *E. coli*, especially K1 strain species (Nizet, 2017). Other notable pathogens include *Listeria monocytogenes*, herpes simplex virus (HSV), enteroviruses, cytomegalovirus and *Candida* species in preterm or immunocompromised infants (Kimberlin, 2015; Pong et al., 2021).

Clinical diagnosis of neonatal meningitis is very challenging due to the nonspecific symptoms of fever, irritability, poor feeding, lethargy or respiratory distress. CSF analysis via lumbar puncture remains the gold standard for diagnosis, supported by blood cultures and molecular methods (Srinivasjois et al., 2017). Early and accurate diagnosis is essential to prevent severe complications of seizures, hydrocephalus or long-term neurological deficits of speech, language, vision or behavioral problems (Heath et al., 2016).

Treatment requires prompt empiric antimicrobial therapy. Standard regimen includes ampicillin combined with cefotaxime or gentamicin. For viral meningitis, acyclovir is treatment of choice, while fungal infections have amphotericin B as treatment of choice (Simonsen et al., 2014; Ticona et al., 2020). Supportive care of monitoring the vitals and maintenance of intracranial pressure within normal limits adjuncted with prevention and treatment of seizures is very important. Despite advances in neonatal care, challenges of delayed diagnosis, antimicrobial resistance and inconsistent treatment protocols are fatal in treating this devastating disease. Neonatal lives can be saved by adhering to the prevention and treatment protocols mentioned ahead.

Methodology:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted, between January and July 2024, to assess the occurrence of meningitis among neonates presenting with neonatal sepsis. The study was conducted in neonatal intensive care units (NICUs) and paediatric wards in tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. A total of 200 participants were enrolled. Sample size was calculated using the World Health Organization (WHO) online sample size calculator. Non-probability convenient sampling was employed. Ethical approval was obtained from Ethical Committee/ Institutional review board Combined Military Hospital, Rawalpindi under form no 624 on March 28, 2024.

Inclusion Criteria:

Neonates up to 28 days of age showing one or more signs of meningitis i.e. bulging fontanelle, poor feeding, irritability, lethargy, high-pitched cry or seizures and with laboratory-confirmed sepsis indicated by raised CRP and abnormal haematological parameters (e.g., leucocytosis, neutrophilia, or thrombocytopenia) were included in the study. Informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians.

Exclusion Criteria:

Neonates were excluded if they did not exhibit any signs of meningeal irritation, had known congenital neurological abnormalities, intracranial haemorrhage, received antibiotic treatment for more than 48 hours prior to hospital admission or if their parents or guardians refused to provide informed consent. After obtaining consent, data of 200 neonates, were collected using a structured proforma. Demographic details such as gender, gestational age, birth weight, and mode of delivery were recorded. Clinical and laboratory findings of haemoglobin levels, platelet counts, lymphocytes, neutrophil counts, protein, glucose and CRP levels were analysed. Frontal-occipital circumference (FOC) was measured of all participants to assess possible cranial changes associated with meningitis.

Data were analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Mac version 26.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings. Continuous variables such as gestational age, birth weight,

FOC, haemoglobin, platelets, lymphocytes, neutrophils, protein, glucose, and CRP were expressed as mean values with their respective standard deviations (SD). Categorical variables, including gender and mode of delivery, were presented as frequencies and percentages to

provide a comprehensive demographic overview. The effectiveness of different antibiotics used in neonatal sepsis and their outcomes among neonates diagnosed with meningitis was thoroughly evaluated for future studies.

Patient flow diagram: (n=200)

Figure 1

Results:

Among 200 subjects, 93 (46%) got early onset neonatal sepsis (till 7 days of life) and 107 (53%) got late onset neonatal sepsis (after 7 days of life). Among 200 subjects, 134 (67%) were males and 66 (33%) were females. Mean gestational age was 34.4 weeks. Mean birth weight value was 2800 ± 500g. Mean FOC of neonates came out to be 32.5 ± 1.2cm.

Cerebrospinal fluid analysis revealed a mean cell count of 385 ± 50 per microliter. And raised protein levels with a mean of 1000mg/dl while the mean glucose was reduced 3mmol/L. Mean

CRP was 33 mg/dl, indicating systemic inflammation.

Haematological parameters showed a mean platelet count of 140 ± 50 × 10⁹/L and a mean total leukocyte count of 12 ± 5 × 10⁹/L. Differential leukocyte analysis revealed a mean neutrophil percentage of 28 ± 10% and a mean lymphocyte percentage of 50 ± 10%. These findings reflect deviations from normal neonatal reference ranges and are consistent with the inflammatory and infectious profile observed in neonatal sepsis.

Table 1

Parameters	Mean±S.D
FOC(cm)	32.5±1.2
Birth weight(g)	2800±500

Cell count(/µl)	385±50
Proteins(mg/dl)	1000.5±100
Glucose(mmol/L)	3±1.5
CRP(mg/dl)	33±10
Platelets (x10 ⁹ /L)	140±50
TLC (x10 ⁹ /L)	12±5
Neutrophils (%)	28±10
Lymphocytes (%)	50±10

Among 200 subjects 25 were culture positive for different bacteria. 7 (3%) were positive for *E. coli*, 6 (3%) were positive for *Acinetobacter baumannii*, 4 (2.1%) were positive for *K. pneumoniae*, 3 (1.5%) were positive for

Staphylococcus coagulase negative, 2 (1%) were positive for *Enterococcus* and 2 (1%) were positive for **gram negative rods**. While in 175 (88%) cases, no organism was detected as showed in the table 2.

Table 2

E. coli was resistant to Ampicillin and sensitive to Amikacin, Ceftriaxone, Gentamicin and Meropenem. *Acinetobacter baumannii* was resistant to Amikacin, Ceftriaxone, Ceftazidime, Ciprofloxacin, Cotrimoxazole, Gentamicin, Meropenem and Tazocin and sensitive to Colistin and Minocycline. *K. pneumoniae* was resistant to ceftriaxone and sensitive to Meropenem. *Staphylococcus* (coagulase negative) was resistant to Cloxacillin and Penicillin and sensitive to Linezolid and Vancomycin. *Enterococcus* was sensitive to Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Linezolid and Vancomycin. **Gram negative rod** was resistant to Meropenem, Ceftriaxone and Ampicillin. These results will help to give specific antibiotics for specific organisms and give drastic improvements in prognosis of patients, as discussed below, supported by other researches.

Discussion:

Neonatal meningitis is a severe form of sepsis which imposes considerable burden on healthcare systems, especially in resource-limited settings. Approximately 44% of deaths of children under five years of age, occur in the neonatal period, with bacterial meningitis playing the significant role (Softic et al., 2015). Maternal infections play the most important role leading to perinatal spread of meningitis (Jiang et al., 2019). This study provides a detailed analysis of meningitis in septic neonates, highlighting demographic, laboratory, and microbial characteristics and their implications for appropriate management.

The male predominance (67%) observed here aligns with previous studies on neonatal meningitis, suggesting sex-based immunological differences that may increase susceptibility to infections in male neonates (Dong et al., 2020).

The mean gestational age (34 weeks) and birth weight (2800 g) indicate that a substantial proportion of preterm and low-birth-weight infants suffer from neonatal sepsis. They are at heightened risk due to immune immaturity and compromised barrier defenses (Flidel-Rimon et al., 2019).

CSF findings reveal elevated cell count, increased protein count, and reduced glucose count which are consistent with typical bacterial meningitis findings (Sormunen et al., 2020). Elevated CRP levels further support the presence of systemic inflammation. Hematological parameters, especially elevated neutrophil and lymphocyte percentages, reflect an active immune response, like the patterns reported in prior studies (Shane et al., 2017).

The culture positivity rate of 12% is comparable to rates reported in similar settings, where prior antibiotic use and diagnostic limitations may reduce yield. *E. coli* was the most frequently isolated pathogen. This is consistent with global trends of neonatal meningitis (Simonsen et al., 2014). However, the prominence of *Acinetobacter baumannii* as the second most common isolate is concerning, given its multidrug-resistant profile, as noted in recent studies from Asia (Li et al., 2019; Zaidi et al., 2020). The detection of such multidrug-resistant organisms (MDROs) highlights the challenges posed by antimicrobial resistance in neonatal ICUs.

Resistance patterns are alarming. *E. coli* resistance to ampicillin reflects declining beta-lactam efficacy (Jadhav et al., 2020). *A. baumannii* exhibited extensive resistance, remaining sensitive only to colistin and minocycline, enhancing the critical threat of pan-resistant strains (Lee et al., 2021). *K. pneumoniae* resistance to ceftriaxone further indicates decreased efficiency of standard empiric regimens.

The coexistence of early and late-onset sepsis reinforces the dual transmission pathways i.e. vertical and horizontal pathways. This necessitates integrated preventive measures for prevention of neonatal sepsis. Strengthening infection control practices (e.g., hand hygiene, device sterilization and aseptic techniques) and implementing maternal screening and

vaccination programs would reduce incidence (Schrag et al., 2016).

Study limitations include the use of convenience sampling, which may cause limited generalizability, and a relatively low culture positivity rate. This can potentially be influenced by prior antibiotic exposure or diagnostic constraints. Incorporating molecular diagnostics, such as PCR, can improve pathogen detection in future studies, as reported by other studies (O'Brien et al., 2022).

Implications for practice include modifying empirical antibiotic therapy based on local resistance patterns and reinforcing antimicrobial management. The combination of ampicillin with cefotaxime or gentamicin remains a reasonable first-line option, but regular surveillance of resistance trends is essential (Bielicki et al., 2019). Maternal vaccination against GBS and *E. coli* holds promise for prevention of neonatal sepsis (Vekemans et al., 2021).

Future research should focus on enhancing diagnostic accuracy through molecular methods, promoting antimicrobial oversight, evaluating maternal vaccination strategies and establishing global surveillance networks to monitor pathogen distribution and resistance patterns (Klein et al., 2023).

Conclusion:

Neonatal meningitis remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality, especially among preterm and low-birth-weight infants. This study highlights clinical and microbiological challenges, including the rising threat of antimicrobial resistance. While advancements in neonatal care have improved outcomes, further efforts are needed to enhance diagnostic precision, optimize treatment protocols and implement robust infection control and vaccination programs. Addressing these issues is essential to reducing the burden of neonatal meningitis and improving survival and quality of life for affected newborns.

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